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	17.11.2022	Pirjo Nikander (TAU)	Updates on Implementation of the pilot course in Supervision in TAU
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Deliverable D3.4

D3.4 Implementation of the pilot course in Supervision

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The DocEnhance deliverable no. 3.4 Implementation of the pilot course in Supervision provides an overview on implementation of the pilot course in Supervision at three universities in Finland, Slovakia, and Spain. The introduction provides a short overview of the supervision course creation and implementation procedures. The second section is devoted to a short description of piloting universities, namely Tampere University in Finland, Matej Bel University in Slovakia, and the University of Alcalá in Spain. The third section describes the Supervision course and offers technical information related to the implementation of the Supervision course in DocEnhance project. In its first subsection, it describes the content of the supervision course developed in the DocEnhance project, while its second subsection described the process of its implementation in three EU universities in two loops. The fourth section briefly summarizes the evaluation of supervision course implementation realized within DocEnhance project, while this chapter is divided into quantitative and qualitative results and compares the evaluation in two loops.

Altogether, 138 supervisors at three EU universities participated in two loops of the implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course. The KPI set in a proposal was that two universities (UAH and UMB) would implement the Supervision course in both loops. Tampere University voluntary joined and implemented the Supervision course in both loops, which was an added value to the DocEnhance project.

1. INTRODUCTION

This task involves the actual implementation and running of the pilot course in supervision. The course was run at three universities instead of two initially planned universities (Matej Bel University in Slovakia, and the University of Alcalá in Spain). Tampere University in Finland voluntarily implemented the Supervision course. The content of the course was mainly developed by Tampere University and run through their Moodle on which they kindly provided access to universities that implemented the course in order to be able to use all materials, videos, etc. The first loop was followed by the evaluation (WP4) and feedback. Afterwards, based on the feedback from evaluation of the first loop, changes were made to refine the course (WP2). The updated course was run in the second loop to obtain the final deliverables of WP2 and WP3.

2. PILOTING UNIVERSITIES

The Supervision course was piloted for a proof-of-concept by selected partner universities, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, in order to assess the applicability of the concept across Europe. The Supervision course was run by Tampere University in Finland, Matej Bel University in Slovakia, and the University of Alcalá in Spain.

TAMPERE UNIVERSITY (FINLAND)

Tampere University (TAU) provides a space for doctoral researchers to develop both their research and innovation activities and transferable skills in multidisciplinary learning and lifelong partnerships. The developed applications of TAU aim to benefit industry, business and the public sector. The university continually strengthens the culture of international collaboration and digitalisation of the campus and promotes sustainable societal renewal, social innovation and spear-head research in health, technology and social sciences. Some 220 doctorates are defended on a yearly basis at TAU. The TAU Doctoral School (est. 2011) is an institutional-level doctoral training expert. The Doctoral School supports the thorough and interdisciplinary academic expertise and employability of all doctoral researchers. Together with doctoral programmes, the School offers excellent, systematic, and up-to-date training to all researchers at all career levels. The Doctoral School's courses and other interdisciplinary events bring together the 2200 doctoral-level researchers across all faculties and their 21 doctoral programmes.

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MATEJ BEL UNIVERSITY (SLOVAKIA)

Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica (UMB) is the main comprehensive HEI in Central Slovakia. It has 600 university teachers and researchers and 9,000 students studying at six faculties: Economics, Humanities, Natural Sciences, Political Sciences and International Relations, Education, and Law. UMB was the first Slovak university to receive the award "HR Excellence in Research". International cooperation has been rapidly developing in recent years mainly through numerous EU programmes including FPs. UMB is currently implementing three H2020 projects, Erasmus+ projects and playing a pivotal role in Vision2020, which is a prestigious network of European universities and SMEs aiming at higher participation in H2020. UMB has an advanced infrastructure with sufficient technical equipment that has been improved in recent years with the financial support of European structural funds. All university premises have access to world databases such as Cambridge Journals: Humanities and Social Sciences, Emerald, Scopus, Science Direct, Springer Link, Web of Knowledge, Wiley Online Library, etc. UMB provides ample space and facilities for research, teaching and networking. International cooperation has been rapidly developing in recent years mainly through participation in numerous EU projects under FP5, FP6, FP7 and H2020. UMB furthermore has long-term experience in participation in many other research projects financed by various grant schemes, for example NIL funds, OSF, CEEPUS, Interreg, Erasmus, British KHF, American Express, EEA GRANTS, VISEGRAD, etc.

Experience with supervision training: Doctoral education at Matej Bel University is fragmented across faculties without a university Doctoral School. The supervision training was not developed at Matej Bel University and neither was developed at the country level in Slovakia. Therefore, the pilot courses organized as a part of the DocEnhance project were pilots also at the country level. Activities related to improving the quality of doctoral education and supervision belong to UMB priorities, as both activities are involved in the UMB Action Plan for HRS4R implementation.

UNIVERSITY OF ALCALÁ (SPAIN)

Founded in 1499, the University of Alcalá (UAH) is a public university with more than 28,000 students and 1,900 academic staff. It currently runs 36 degree and 45 master studies on its 3 campuses in the fields of Health, Social Science and Law, Humanities, Science and Engineering and Computer Science. UAH is located in an industrial environment that provides an advantageous situation for the development of research projects in collaboration with private industries. UAH has obtained funding for 8 projects under H2020, one of which is coordinated by UAH. The university has furthermore obtained funding for 29 projects under FP7, four of them as coordinator, and for 28 projects and contracts under different R&I programmes and initiatives in Europe, four of them funded under the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme with two projects coordinated by UAH. The UAH Doctoral School has 30 doctoral programmes with 1729 students enrolled in the 2020-21 academic year. Almost 25% of them are foreign students. UAH has participated in 25 Erasmus+ Programmes from 2014. UAH plays a relevant role in the European PhD Hub project by providing collaborations from the business sector and other stakeholders. UAH is also involved in C3QA, an Erasmus+ Programme to extend the European PhD framework to other non-EU countries such as Ukraine, Mongolia, Armenia,

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and Kazakhstan. In addition, UAH is leading an MSCA Co-fund action entitled “Got Energy Talent”. This action tries to enhance the collaboration among the business and academia sectors by sending PhD researchers out of Spain in order to develop and collect information related to the energy field. UAH has been selected to be part of the European University Alliance for Global Health (EUGLOH) for the period 2023-2027.

3. SUPERVISION COURSE DESCRIPTION AND TECHNICAL INFORMATION RELATED TO IMPLEMENTATION OF SUPERVISION COURSE IN DOCENHANCE PROJECT

The modern doctoral supervision is the act that includes multilevel processes and several actors, requires much collaboration and needs to be well organised. The Supervision course developed within the DocEnhance project contains rich material and assignments that can be used for a variety of supervisors (e.g. supervisors with no experience, experienced supervisors, non-academic supervisors, mixed groups), provides practical tips for PhD supervision, raises some supervision themes to work with individually and also in collaboration in different working contexts. The target group is all doctoral candidates supervisors regardless of their discipline.

3.1 Description of the DocEnhance Supervision course

The objectives and main themes of the Supervision course were as follows:

- to provide crucial information on institutional frameworks, resources, and guidelines for supervisory practices in your university, and internationally,
- to discuss essential pedagogical, as well as the widening research skills that are part and parcel of supervision,
- to help integrate own research mission into supervision practices,
- to break the solitude of supervision perceived as master-apprentice practice behind closed doors, and encourages a more collegial, shared supervision & peer support culture,
- to help participants identify key tensions and dynamics, reflect on local practices, and
- to provide tools and practical resources for participants to further develop their own skills and well-being as supervisors.

Pedagogically, the material is recommended to be used in a way that it encourages supervisors to share good supervision practices and learn from them ('peer group working'). Furthermore, the material aims to support 'learning by doing' in supervision activities, increasing also the collaboration within the university and with non-academia.

The recommended practice to organise a short course is the following:

- a pre-assignment (short video, key reading on the local and international frames of supervision + one or two assignments on individual experience)
- two 3-hour sessions with lectures delivered by experts + peer discussion on key aspects of supervision (online or on-site)

- two structured peer group online meetings before the second day.

The course material is based on and united in three main and broad topics:

1. Introduction to doctoral education and supervision (at your university)

There have been ongoing significant transformations in doctoral education in recent decades. The changes like the numbers and internationalisation of doctoral candidates, diversification of them in terms of background, motivation for study and career trajectories, and also the increase of the regulations in doctoral education (e.g. agreements, guidelines and rules to ensure the quality of supervision), have led to a situation that the doctoral education provides not just training to create new original knowledge but also training towards other competences (Taylor 2012). Among many issues, it is good to be aware of what the general goals internationally and nationally are for doctoral education. But not just this, for each supervisor it is crucial to know his/her university guidelines and practices in relation to the doctoral education. How is doctoral education organised at your university? What are the core guidelines and documents? How is the recruitment of doctoral candidates organised? Does the university offer some common courses? What other kind of training and support is targeted at doctoral candidates? How does your university foster collaborative supervision and collaboration with non-academic sector?

In order to address these challenges, the Supervision course includes the key local, national and international regulations and principles governing doctoral programmes. Also, as the starting point, several academic articles, reports etc. on the PhD supervision and its development are available. At this stage of the Supervision course, participants will be able to recognise and clarify:

- some international guidelines and trends for doctoral education,
- key documents on the roles and responsibilities of the supervisors,
- the rules of permanence or expected timing of the various steps, monitoring of progress in PhD supervision,
- the key actors (academic committees, boards, councils, etc.) at your university in doctoral education and their roles,
- the actors and units that provide training and support for doctoral candidates at your university.

The facilitator/trainer of the course collects and presents the guidelines, information, or links of participating university under each topic. The course facilitator/trainer can invite the university actors from internationalization unit, library (data management etc.). They can join the workshop discussion that will clarify their roles in doctoral education at the particular university.

For the first topic open online material is available including the video lecture, readings list and other external material introducing the participants to the supervision topic and to the local context of doctoral education.

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- this part works as the pre-material for the workshop,
- in this part the participants can find the relevant doctoral education documents and guidelines of the local university,
- the material can also be used individually without group working.

Besides, reading list and proposal of tasks for group/individual work are included.

2. Personal development in supervision

Supervisors are dealing with many issues and challenges such as how to build a favourable environment for a doctoral candidate to do research, how the supervision could focus both on a process and product, and how to develop pedagogically research group working.

The material on this second topic aims to support self-orientated personal development process as the PhD supervisor. The workshop and/or peer group discussions taken as a part of the course helps with this task. In this part of the Supervision training supervisors can identify:

- supervision expertise and the possible needs in its development,
- some good practices that are relevant to be implemented in own supervision activities,
- some practices and experiences in dealing with the difficult supervision situations and cases.

The open online material includes thematically oriented video lectures and reading lists with assignments for personal development activities for supervisors.

The material and resources are used in the interdisciplinary group work within the local academic institution (e.g. workshop) or the material can be used also individually without group working.

3. Regional collaboration in doctoral education

The third topic is devoted to the identification of:

- some practices in organisational collaboration of doctoral education,
- challenges and benefits of organisational collaboration,
- some practices on how to support doctoral candidates in their career planning and how to develop supervision practices in inter-sectoral collaboration.

Open online material includes thematically oriented video lectures and reading lists with the assignments on collaborative doctoral education. The material and resources can be used in discussions (e.g. workshop) in the local academic institution and/ or in regional collaboration with the non-academic sector. The material can also be used individually without group working.

The Supervision course provides some extra open materials such as Handbook for Supervisors of Doctoral Candidates produced by Eurodoc (the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers), Visualising the Degree: A PhD Calendar or the Student-Advisor Expectation Scales worksheet and others. If the participants wish to have ECTS by

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completing the course, the recommendation is to give 1-2 ECTS when all materials and assignments are included in the course. But finally, the university that organises the course decides the amount of ECTS.

3.2 DocEnhance Supervision course implementation

In spring and early summer 2021, the DocEnhance consortium put in place the first implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course (Loop 1), and between May and June 2022 the DocEnhance consortium put in place the second implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course (Loop 2).

Each course was piloted for proof-of-concept by selected partner universities, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, in order to assess the applicability of the concept across Europe.

After each pilot course, participants (supervisors) and organisers (trainers) were invited to complete a brief questionnaire on different aspects of the courses and to provide comments or suggestions for further development and improvement. The Supervision course was run at Tampere University in Finland, Matej Bel University in Slovakia and the University of Alcalá in Spain.

The following two tables show the dates, piloting universities, number of supervisors, and target groups of supervisors at each piloting university. In addition, the form of implementation and language are indicated. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and different pandemic mitigation measures and pandemic restrictions in three piloting countries the implementation of piloting courses had to follow these circumstances.

Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Supervisors)	Target group	Form of implementation	Language
12/02/2021-26/02/2021	Universidad de Alcalá (Spain)	40	Two separate groups: junior and senior supervisors (20 each)	Senior supervisors (blended) - Online session: 1 hour - Face-to-face session: 2 hours Junior supervisors: online - 3 hours.	Spanish
11/05/2021-01/06/2021	Tampere University (Finland)	24	Junior supervisors	Online	English
13/05/2021-03/06/2021	Univerzita Mateja Bela V Banskej Bystrici (Slovakia)	15	All groups of supervisors (junior and senior)	Online	Slovak/English

79 supervisors participated in the first round of implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, almost all sessions were organized

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online in Spanish, Slovak and/or English. Only at UAH was a session organised as a face-to-face meeting. At Tampere University, junior supervisors were a target group. At University of Alcalá the course implementation was divided into two parallel target groups, junior and senior supervisors. At Matej Bel University, this was the first Supervision course ever. The target group was supervisors at all stages of their supervisor careers (junior and senior).

Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Supervisors)	Target group	Form of implementation	Language
17/05/2022-10/06/2022	Universidad de Alcalá (Spain)	32	Two separate groups: junior and senior supervisors (15 and 17 respectively)	Senior supervisors (blended) - Online session: 2 hour - Face-to-face session: 2 hours Junior supervisors: online - 4 hours.	Spanish
11/05/2022-01/06/2022	Tampere University (Finland)	13	Junior supervisors	Online	English
04/05/2022-26/05/2022	Univerzita Mateja Bela V Banskej Bystrici (Slovakia)	14	All groups of supervisors (junior and senior)	Onsite	Slovak/English

59 supervisors participated in the second round of implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course. As in the previous loop, two sessions were organized in Spanish, Slovak, and/or English. At Tampere University, all junior supervisors were the main target group. At the University of Alcalá, the implementation of the course was divided into two parallel groups, junior and senior supervisors. At Matej Bel University, supervisors at all stages of their supervisor careers (junior and senior) were the target group. University of Alcalá organized this loop as hybrid course (online and onsite session), Tampere university organised the course online and Matej Bel University organised the course as face-to-face two sessions.

Altogether, 138 supervisors at three EU universities participated in two loops of the implementation of the DocEnhance Supervision course. The KPI set in a proposal was that two universities (UAH and UMB) will implement the Supervision course in both loops. Tampere University voluntarily implemented the Supervision course in both loops, which was an added value to the DocEnhance project.

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4. EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SUPERVISION COURSE

This section briefly summarizes the evaluation of supervision course implementation realized within DocEnhance project, while this chapter is divided into quantitative results and qualitative results.

4.1 Evaluation of supervision course implementation – quantitative results

The first Supervision loop was implemented in the spring and early summer 2021 and a total 79 supervisors took part in its implementation. 37 supervisors evaluated the first Supervision course which is almost 50% of all participants.

Supervision Course Loop 1				
Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Supervisors)	No. Respondents (Supervisors)	Response Rate
12/02/2021-26/02/2021	Universidad de Alcalá (Spain)	40	32	80,0%
11/05/2021-01/06/2021	Tampere University (Finland)	24	21	87,5%
13/05/2021-03/06/2021	Univerzita Mateja Bela V Banskej Bystrici (Slovakia)	15	6	40,0%
Total		79	37	46,83%

The second supervision loop was implemented in early summer 2022 and 79 supervisors took part in its implementation. 46 supervisors evaluated the second Supervision course which is almost 78% of all participants.

Supervision Course Loop 2				
Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Supervisors)	No. Respondents (Supervisors)	Response Rate
17/05/2022-10/06/2022	Universidad de Alcalá (Spain)	32	26	81,3%
11/05/2022-01/06/2022	Tampere University (Finland)	13	13	100,0%
04/05/2022-26/05/2022	Univerzita Mateja Bela V Banskej Bystrici (Slovakia)	14	7	50,0%
Total		59	46	77,97%

The eight closed-ended questions included in the questionnaires were rate scale responses presented with a continuous scale based on 6 levels (in order to avoid the central tendency of the 3 when working with a scale of 1-5).

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Question	Rating Loop 1	Rating Loop 2
Do you think that the learning outcomes of the course will be useful for your future career development?	5,32	5,53
In your opinion, to what extent are the course guidelines adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,00	5,29
In your opinion, to what extent are the learning materials adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,05	5,35
In your opinion, to what extent are the work methods adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	4,97	5,18
Please give the course an overall assessment	5,16	5,29
To what degree did you achieve your expected learning outcomes?	4,89	5,35
In your opinion, to what extent are the course contents adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,05	5,53
How much time and effort did you need to achieve the course objectives?	3,65	3,65

Generally, both loops of Supervision course implementation were highly rated and in all questions (except the last one) the rating was higher in the second loop, which indicates improvement in the development and implementation of the Supervision course.

Usefulness, course content, and achievement of expected learning outcomes were the highest rated items. The time and effort required to achieve the course objectives was reported to be adequate. In addition, all participants in the Supervision would recommend the DocEnhance courses to other students in both loops.

To what degree did you achieve your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	0,0%	2,7%	29,7%	43,3%	24,3%	4,89
Supervision Loop 2	45	0,0%	0,0%	2,2%	8,9%	53,3%	35,6%	5,22

The participants' expectations about the learning outcomes of the Supervision were generally satisfied to a high degree. The Supervision course, with a global score of 4,89 for the first loop and 5,22 for the second loop met the participant's expectations very well or completely in 67,7% for the first loop and 88,9% for the second loop. The Supervision course improved its global scores with respect to those received after the first implementation of the pilot course, namely 0,33 points higher.

In your opinion, to what extent are the course guidelines adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	36	0,0%	2,8%	0,0%	25,0%	38,9%	33,3%	5,00
Supervision Loop 2	47	0,0%	0,0%	6,4%	12,8%	55,3%	25,5%	5,00

The supervision course guidelines were generally considered to be very well (38,9% for the first loop and 55,3% for the second) or completely (33,3% for the first loop and 25,5% for the second loop) adapted to the expected learning outcomes of the participants. Results for the Supervision course indicate that 72,2% of participants in the first loop and 80,8% of the second loop consider that the course guidelines were very well or completely adapted to their expected learning outcomes. The global score for the Supervision course remained unchanged.

In your opinion, to what extent are the work methods adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	0,0%	5,4%	29,7%	27,0%	37,9%	4,97
Supervision Loop 2	46	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%	19,6%	41,3%	34,8%	5,07

Regarding to the adaptation of course work methods to expected learning outcomes, participants reported that the work methods used in the Supervision courses were very well (27,0 % for the first loop and 41,3% for the second loop) or completely (37,9% for the first loop and 34,8% for the second loop) adapted to expected learning outcomes. Results for the Supervision course indicate that 64,9 % of participants in the first loop and 76,1 % for the second loop consider that the work methods were very well or completely adapted to their expected learning outcomes. Compared to the results obtained after the first implementation of the pilot course, the global score for the Supervision course improved slightly for the second loop (+ 0,10 points).

In your opinion, to what extent are the course contents adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	0,0%	5,4%	18,9%	40,5%	35,2%	5,05
Supervision Loop 2	46	0,0%	0,0%	6,5%	15,2%	37,0%	41,3%	5,13

The satisfaction of the participants with the content of the course was similar, the participants reported that the content of the course used in the Supervision courses was very well (40,5 % for the first loop and 37,0 % for the second loop) or completely (35,2 % for the first loop and 41,3 % for the second loop) adapted to the expected learning outcomes. Results for the Supervision course indicate that 75,7 % of participants in the first loop and 78,3 % for the second loop consider that the work methods were very well or completely adapted to their expected learning outcomes. Compared to the results obtained after the first implementation of the pilot course, the global score for the Supervision course improved slightly for the second loop (+ 0,08 points).

In your opinion, to what extent are the learning materials adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	0,0%	5,4%	21,6%	35,1%	37,8%	5,05
Supervision Loop 2	46	0,0%	2,2%	6,5%	10,9%	39,1%	41,3%	5,11

7 out of 10 participants in the Supervision course thought that the learning materials were very well adapted (35,1%) or completely adapted (37,8%) in loop 1, while participants in the Supervision course loop 2 thought that the learning materials were very well adapted (39,1%) or completely adapted (41,3%). Results for the Supervision course indicate that 72,9 % of participants in the first loop and 80,4 % for the second loop consider that the learning materials were very well or completely adapted to their expected learning outcomes. Compared to the results obtained after the first implementation of the pilot course, the global score for the Supervision course again improved slightly for the second loop (+ 0,06 points).

How much time and effort did you need to achieve the course objectives? (1: very little; 2: a little; 3: adequate; 4: a bit more than expected; 5: very much; 6: too much)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	8,1%	8,1%	13,5%	54,1%	13,5%	2,7%	3,65
Supervision Loop 2	46	2,2%	23,9%	47,8%	15,2%	8,7%	2,2%	3,11

The majority of participants (67,6 for the first loop and 63%) considered the time and effort required to achieve course objectives adequate (13,5% for the first loop and 47,8 % for the second loop) or slightly more than expected (54,1 % for the first loop and 15,2 % for the second loop).

Do you think that the learning outcomes of the course will be useful for your future career development? (1: not at all; 2: very little; 3: somewhat; 4: a lot; 5: very much; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	13,5%	40,5%	46,0%	5,32
Supervision Loop 2	46	0,0%	4,3%	2,2%	13,0%	47,8%	32,6%	5,02

When asked if the learning outcomes obtained through the DocEnhance Supervision course will be useful for their future career development, 8 out of 10 participants (86,5 % for the first loop and 80,4 % for the second loop) considered that they would be very useful or completely useful.

On the other end of the balance, zero % of respondents for the first loop and second loop replied that the Supervision course would not be useful for their future career development at all. For the second loop 4,3 % of respondents thought that the Supervision course would be useful for their future career development only a very little. Participants gave the courses a global score of 5,32 for the first loop and 5,02 for the second loop.

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Please give the course an overall assessment. (1: very poor; 2: poor; 3: average; 4: good; 5: very good; 6: excellent)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Supervision Loop 1	37	0,0%	2,7%	0,0%	13,5%	46,0%	37,8%	5,16
Supervision Loop 2	46	0,0%	2,2%	2,2%	10,9%	50,0%	34,8%	5,13

In the first loop, 83,8% of respondents rated the Supervision course as excellent (37,8%) or very good (46%) and the course received a global score of 5,16. In the second loop, 84,8% of respondents rated the Supervision course as excellent (34,8%) or very good (50,0%). The course also received a global score of 5,13. When asked if they would recommend the courses to other supervisors, all responded 'yes'.

4.2 Evaluation of the implementation of the supervision course – qualitative results

The course was designed with the objective of streamlining the management of PhD supervisors at the piloting universities, creating a forum for discussion, identifying relevant aspects of doctoral studies, and improving quality in supervision practices.

Supervisors believed that the most important things they learned in the Supervision course were supervision roles, models, tools, resources, and practices (43,3%); importance of communication/dialogue and active listening in the supervision process (23,3%); exchange of experiences/good practices with colleagues and peers (20,0%). Supervisors highlighted group discussions as the most relevant aspect of the Supervision course, with a special focus on peer discussion groups and brainstorming sessions (27,7%).

Although participants in the Supervision course expressed their satisfaction with the course, only 6,4% did not make any suggestions for further course development and/or improvement.

The remaining 93,6% of the participants made numerous suggestions for general course improvement. Responses have been grouped into the following categories: student profile; interaction; course content; learning materials and methods; course duration. The summary of responses offers the following table.

Supervisor profile	"Since participants came from very different disciplines, the problems and solutions addresses were not always applicable to others".
	"Maybe the course should be tailored to different doctoral schools, or at least thematic bundles of them (it is not very useful to have exchanges between medical researchers and gamification researchers, the context and practices are so different)".
Interaction	"More peer-to-peer discussions".
	"More space for discussing, and creating time and space for reflection and exchange of information".

	<p>"This kind of education should be held face-to-face".</p> <p>"I would like to meet in smaller, multilingual and multicultural groups".</p> <p>"Perhaps more debate among the attendees about specific examples of problems that can occur when directing or co-directing a doctoral thesis would have been enriching".</p>
Course content	<p>"I would have liked to have some contents that engaged more critically the practice of supervision".</p> <p>"Include sessions on leadership and motivation".</p> <p>"More practical case studies".</p>
Learning materials and methods	<p>"High-level, too abstract material"</p> <p>"More practical examples instead of "nice sounding" abstract/high-level and generic material".</p> <p>"Sometimes, the slides contained too much information and it was a bit difficult to follow".</p> <p>"Sessions could focus less on going through slides (they could be shared beforehand) and more on sharing of experiences".</p> <p>"Perhaps more variation and rhythm amidst each session, e.g. smaller group meetings, videos, discussions after the watching".</p> <p>"Too many videos!! They are definitely not the best material to utilize in teaching".</p> <p>"Less videos, more articles for reading".</p> <p>"More team exercises, less writing".</p> <p>"Moodle page is not clear".</p> <p>"Too much homework".</p>
Course duration	<p>"A little bit longer course?"</p> <p>"It was very short, especially for a senior workshop. Many aspects could be addressed in greater depth."</p> <p>"It could be a little longer and with a little more practical exercises".</p> <p>"The live sessions were quite long and one gets quite tired afterwards. I would arrange one more session but shorten each session".</p> <p>"Perhaps shorter sessions, but a few more".</p> <p>"The duration of the sessions could be extended by half an hour".</p> <p>"Extending the duration of the course so that there are no problems in finishing/seeing all the aspects".</p>

The most frequently recurring recommendations were related to interaction and the need to create space for discussion, reflection, and exchange of information and experience. Participants in the Supervision course would also appreciate a longer format of the course divided into at least two (or more, but shorter) sessions. Participants also suggest to organise this type of training as face-to-face meetings, and it needs to be considered if disciplines of supervisor are not too different in order to ensure relevant exchange of information and experience for all participants.

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REFERENCES

DocEnhance Deliverable No. 4.2 Evaluation of First Implementation of Pilot Courses
Docenhance Deliverable No. 4.5 Evaluation of Second Implementation of Pilot Courses

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 THE PROMOTION LEAFLETS FOR THE SUPERVISION COURSES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society programme under grant agreement no. 872483

Supervision course leaflets from Matej Bel University in Slovakia

<p>DocEnhance Supervision Workshop</p> <p>Workshop pre školiteľov doktorandov UMB zameraný na zefektívnenie vedenia doktorandov školiteľmi Forma workshopu: online</p> <p>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 872483</p>	
<p>DocEnhance Supervision Workshop</p> <p>Workshop pre školiteľov doktorandov UMB zameraný na zefektívnenie vedenia doktorandov školiteľmi: Dobrá prax vedenia doktorandov</p> <p>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 872483</p>	

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ANNEX 2 PICTURES FROM SUPERVISION COURSE IMPLEMENTATION

Supervision course implementation at Matej Bel University in Slovakia

Online Supervision course Loop 1

Face-to-face Supervision course Loop 2